

health **RI**

enabling data driven health

**ETH Knowledge Exchange Workshop
on FAIR implementation**

21 November 2022

ZonMw

Welcome & introduction

Fieke Schoots (Health-RI) & Angela Lansbergen-Engel (ZonMW)

- Welcome
 - First [meeting](#) March 2016: FAIR data stewardship and Data Management Plans for DTL Hotel Managers
 - Second [meeting](#) March 2018: A FAIR afternoon: on FAIR data stewardship for Technology Hotel (/ETH4) beneficiaries
 - Today: current state of affairs and common goals
- Agenda :
 - Part I: Introduction and best practices
 - Part II: Exchange ideas on achievements, challenges and future activities for FAIR implementation at the Technology Hotels

Agenda

- 13:00 *Welcome* – Fieke Schoots (Health-RI) & Angela Lansbergen-Engel
Introduction in the Technology Hotels – Ruben Kok (Director DTL / CSA Health-RI)
Introduction in the Enabling Technology Hotels programme and its FAIR aims
– Margreet Bloemers (Project leader FAIR data & data management ZonMW)
- 13:30 *USEQ (Utrecht Sequencing Facility) and FAIRness via the EGA* – Anke Wegman, UMCU
FAIR implementation at the Genomics Coordination Center – Joeri van der Velde, Aneas Hodselmans, UMCG
The Implementation and Demonstration of the X-omics FAIR Data Cube – XiaoFeng Liao, Radboud UMC
- 14:30 Break
- 15:00 Discussion in groups - All
- 16:15 Wrap up and Closure
- 16:30 Drinks

Technology Hotels – Ruben Kok (DTL / Health-RI)

Introduction in the Technology Hotels

- Initiative of DTL and ZonMw/NWO
- Small projects (30 k EURO) each, to familiarize researchers with the capacities of shared research facilities, and the possibilities offered by advanced life sciences technologies (genomics, metabolomics, proteomics, transcriptomics, imaging, bioinformatics, ...)
- Five rounds of projects funded, in total well over 150 projects
- Basis to generate high quality FAIR data with rich provenance
- Link to Health-RI, DCCs, ELIXIR, ...

“A short history of nearly everything”

Why does ZonMw require RDM & FAIR data?

> improve impact of research outputs and accelerate innovation!

□ Enable data reuse and data sharing:

- Allow other researchers to build upon existing data and knowledge (return on investment)
- Accelerate knowledge and innovation for improving health
- Enrich research (combining datasets)
- Pattern recognition in large datasets

Data and other research outputs, e.g.:

Biological materials, recordings, images, etc.

□ Enable verification of research results:

- Research integrity, responsible science
- Reproduction research

□ Ensure added value for the researcher!

- The first to benefit from RDM and FAIRification
- Quality improvement

1. Data management (stewardship)

2. Making data FAIR!

Funder's role in FAIR implementation activities

- ❑ Initiated – developed in ZonMw's COVID-19 programme
- ❑ ZonMw – Health-RI – GFF
- ❑ FIP – M4M – FDP
- ❑ Support & community building

Funding agency sets requirements

researcher

**Data steward
at univ/umc/hs**

health
RI research infrastructure

DTL

GO FAIR

Experts at FAIR data services & research infrastructures

Landelijk Coördinatiepunt
Research Data Management

Thematic DCCs
Local Digital Competence Centres

Phases in creating and using FAIR data

CEDAR Workbench

- Metadata schema > template > form to be "filled in"
- The "questions"

- Controlled vocabularies
- Drop-downs and autocomplete
- The "answers"

Project Cedar - Metadata Editor

COVID-19 Project Content_V5

Read & Understood

Read & Understood*

Project Title (1..N)

Project Title - Multiple answers are allowed.*

Language*

Scope

Focus Area

To which focus area of the ZonMw COVID-19 program does your project belong?*

Most projects have been classified by ZonMw in one of these focus areas. If you can not find your focus area, please contact us.

For all terms provided in the drop-down list it is useful to check the definitions in BioPortal <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ZONMW-CONTENT>.

care and prevention - care and prevention for vulnerable citizens

care and prevention - organisation of care and prevention

care and prevention - palliative care and bereavement

care and prevention - transmission and epidemiology

effects on society - impacts of measurements and strategies

effects on society - impacts of measurements and strategies

Area Level (1..N)

Area Level - Multiple answers are allowed.

Disease (1..N)

Which category of diseases, if any, is relevant for your project? Multiple answers are allowed.

If you ticked human disease, what specific disease is relevant for your project?

Discuss options for ETH related metadata:

What is FAIR?

How would you describe the technologies?

Which elements must be included in the metadata scheme

for a standardised description of the hotel technology?

R1.2 (Meta)data are associated with detailed **provenance**

Box 2 | The FAIR Guiding Principles

<https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. (meta)(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Automating F, A, I, and R

Best practice: USEQ (Utrecht Sequencing Facility) and FAIRness via the EGA – Anke Wegman, UMCU

Anke Wegman is a postdoc Data Steward at the Center for Molecular Medicine (CMM) at the UMC Utrecht. She has a background in Medicine, Epidemiology, Data Management and Data Stewardship. Her focus is to promote – and advice on how – to practice Open Science, within the privacy regulations and according to the FAIR principles. As a member of the DAC (Data Access Committee) for the EGA (European Genome-Phenome Archive), she reviews access requests to datasets stored in the EGA.

Best practice: FAIR implementation at the Genomics Coordination Center – Joeri van der Velde, Aneas Hodselmans, UMCG

- **Joeri van der Velde** is a postdoc bioinformatician on a mission to make life sciences data FAIR. He is the lead author of “FAIR Genomes metadata schema promoting Next Generation Sequencing data reuse in Dutch healthcare and research”, is a FAIRification Steward in EJP-RD, and is now working on ‘FAIR Data Hub’ as part of the next generation MOLGENIS platform, which brings together popular semantic data standards and APIs for quick and seamless FAIRification.
- **Aneas Hodselmans** is a data-manager at the Department of Genetics at the University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG). He is a data expert in catalogs, and FAIR data-management. In recent years he has extended his expertise by managing the data of catalogs (including BBMRI-ERIC Directory and RD-Connect) and advising about data-management plans.

Best practice: The Implementation and Demonstration of the X-omics FAIR Data Cube – XiaoFeng Liao, Radboud UMC

XiaoFeng Liao is a data steward at the Center for Molecular and Biomolecular Informatics (CMBI) at Radboud UMC. He is working on “FAIR Data Cube” in the X-omics initiative, where his main objective is to develop infrastructure that helps researchers in different stages of the Research Data Life Cycle including creating and describing new data, and finding, understanding, and reusing existing FAIR multi-omics data. He is also involved in other FAIR-related projects, for example, the PRISMA studies, where he is mainly responsible for developing a FAIR data model for breast cancer screening.

Discussion in groups

Questions / statements by speakers (Anke Wegman)

- ***Agree or disagree:***
- When applying for a grant, the funder should check:
 - a) if the data are allowed to be shared (under restriction) afterwards
 - b) if the repository the researcher is planning to use is suitable/allowed.

Aneas & Joeri:

“It is not our differences that divide us. It is our inability to recognize, accept, and celebrate those differences.” — Audre Lorde

standardization

“If you think good ~~architecture~~ is expensive, try bad ~~architecture~~. — Brian Foote and Joseph Yoder”

standardization

Embrace local differences, unite by global standards

Margreet

Which elements must be included in the metadata scheme for a standardised description of hotel technology?

Discussion points

- Role funder in checking if data can be shared and use of repository
 - Can access control be automated?
- Embrace local differences, unite by global standards
- Which elements must be included in the metadata scheme for a standardised description of hotel technology?

Findings from earlier meetings

- **2016 Fair data stewardship and Data management plans for DTL Hotel managers**

From [report](#) about Gabino Sanchez Perez (Wageningen UR) [presentation](#): “Another challenge is to deal with new standards, as often these are not established (yet), especially for innovative techniques.”

- **2018 A FAIR afternoon: on FAIR data stewardship for Technology Hotel (/ETH4) beneficiaries**

Michel Dumontier : “If we are ever to realize the full potential of content we create then we must find ways to reduce the barrier to (automatically) find and reuse that content. To achieve this objective we must build a *social* and *technological* infrastructure for the discovery and assessment of digital resources”

Discussion in groups

Please make notes for each table / group so that we can use them for the report. Note for the central wrap-up :

1. What has been achieved in implementing FAIR at the Technology Hotels? Think about progress made in ‘technological’ and ‘social’ infrastructure (standards, tool, data stewardship, etc.).
1. What are remaining challenges for making data FAIR at the technology hotels? Think about the full ‘journey’, from the first contact to the closure of a project.
1. What can be done jointly to remove barriers and further implement FAIR?

Wrap up and Closure
16:15 - 16:30

Wrap up & Closure

Pitch per table about your take aways

Closure

- Are there any topics that we did not discuss yet?
- Next steps:
 - Share presentations, notes and report
 -

Drinks
16:30 - 17:30